

TOCCATA E FUGA

PER QUARTETTO DI CLARINETTI

IN MI MINORE

dalla TOCCATA E FUGA IN RE MINORE BWV 565 di J.S. BACH

Adagio ($\text{♩} = 44$)

Trascriz. di CASADEI DIEGO

Lento

I CLAR.
(Sib)

II CLAR.
(Sib)

III CLAR.
(Sib)

CLAR.
BASSO
(Sib)

Restissimo ($\text{♩} = 84$)

I

II

BASSO

I

II

III

BASSO

molto rall.

Allegro moderato ($\text{♩} = 56$)

Handwritten musical score for the first system, featuring four staves with treble clefs and a key signature of one sharp (F#). The music includes various rhythmic patterns and dynamic markings. The first staff has a tempo marking *tatt.* (ritardando) above it. The second and third staves also have *tatt.* markings. The fourth staff has a *tatt.* marking and a sharp sign (#) above it. The system concludes with a double bar line and a fermata over the final note.

Handwritten musical score for the second system, featuring four staves with treble clefs and a key signature of one sharp (F#). The music continues with complex rhythmic figures. The first staff has a tempo marking *tatt.* (ritardando) above it. The system concludes with a double bar line and a fermata over the final note.

Handwritten musical score for the third system, featuring four staves with treble clefs and a key signature of one sharp (F#). The first staff is marked *libero* and contains complex rhythmic patterns. The second, third, and fourth staves are mostly blank, with some markings and a fermata. The system concludes with a double bar line and a fermata over the final note.

Handwritten musical score for the first system, consisting of four staves. The top staff features complex rhythmic patterns with many beamed notes. The second staff has a similar pattern with some rests. The third and fourth staves are simpler, with fewer notes and some rests. The key signature has one sharp (F#).

Prestissimo (♩ = 86)

Handwritten musical score for the second system, consisting of four staves. The top staff has a few notes followed by a rest. The second and third staves have triplets of eighth notes. The fourth staff has a few notes followed by a rest. The key signature has one sharp (F#).

Handwritten musical score for the third system, consisting of four staves. The top staff has a few notes followed by a rest. The second and third staves have eighth notes with beamed pairs. The fourth staff has a few notes followed by a rest. The key signature has one sharp (F#).

Maestoso (♩=84)

Handwritten musical score for the first system, featuring four staves with treble clefs and a key signature of one sharp (F#). The music includes various rhythmic patterns such as eighth notes, quarter notes, and triplets, with some notes marked with '+' signs. The first staff has a key signature change to two sharps (F#, C#) in the second measure.

(♩=84)
(Fuga)

Handwritten musical score for the second system, featuring four staves with treble clefs and a key signature of one sharp (F#). The music includes various rhythmic patterns such as eighth notes, quarter notes, and triplets, with some notes marked with '+' signs. The first staff has a key signature change to two sharps (F#, C#) in the second measure.

Handwritten musical score for the third system, featuring four staves with treble clefs and a key signature of one sharp (F#). The music includes various rhythmic patterns such as eighth notes, quarter notes, and triplets, with some notes marked with '+' signs. The first staff has a key signature change to two sharps (F#, C#) in the second measure.

Handwritten musical score system 1, consisting of four staves. The top staff contains a melody with quarter notes and rests. The second staff contains a melody with half notes and rests. The third staff contains a complex rhythmic pattern with many sixteenth notes and some plus signs. The bottom staff contains rests.

Handwritten musical score system 2, consisting of four staves. The top staff continues the melody with some plus signs. The second staff contains a melody with half notes and eighth notes. The third staff contains a complex rhythmic pattern with many sixteenth notes and plus signs. The bottom staff contains a melody with eighth notes and a sharp sign at the end.

Handwritten musical score system 3, consisting of four staves. The top staff contains a complex rhythmic pattern with many sixteenth notes and plus signs. The second staff contains a melody with eighth notes and plus signs. The third staff contains a melody with eighth notes and plus signs. The bottom staff contains a melody with eighth notes and plus signs.

Handwritten musical score for the first system, consisting of four staves. The top staff features a complex melodic line with many beamed notes and a final triplet. The second and third staves contain rhythmic accompaniment with triplets and chords. The bottom staff continues the accompaniment with chords and some melodic fragments.

Handwritten musical score for the second system, consisting of four staves. The top staff has a melodic phrase with a triplet. The second staff has a melodic line with a triplet. The third staff has a melodic line with a triplet. The bottom staff has a melodic line with a triplet.

Handwritten musical score for the third system, consisting of four staves. The top staff has a melodic line with a triplet. The second staff has a melodic line with a triplet. The third staff has a melodic line with a triplet. The bottom staff has a melodic line with a triplet.

Handwritten musical notation for the first system, consisting of four staves. The notation includes various notes, rests, and accidentals. The first staff features a sequence of notes with a sharp sign, followed by a rest and a note with a sharp sign. The second staff shows a series of notes with a sharp sign, followed by a rest and a note with a sharp sign. The third staff contains a note with a sharp sign, followed by a rest and a note with a sharp sign. The fourth staff shows a note with a sharp sign, followed by a rest and a note with a sharp sign.

Handwritten musical notation for the second system, consisting of four staves. The notation includes various notes, rests, and accidentals. The first staff features a note with a sharp sign, followed by a rest and a note with a sharp sign. The second staff shows a series of notes with a sharp sign, followed by a rest and a note with a sharp sign. The third staff contains a note with a sharp sign, followed by a rest and a note with a sharp sign. The fourth staff shows a note with a sharp sign, followed by a rest and a note with a sharp sign.

Handwritten musical notation for the third system, consisting of four staves. The notation includes various notes, rests, and accidentals. The first staff features a note with a sharp sign, followed by a rest and a note with a sharp sign. The second staff shows a series of notes with a sharp sign, followed by a rest and a note with a sharp sign. The third staff contains a note with a sharp sign, followed by a rest and a note with a sharp sign. The fourth staff shows a note with a sharp sign, followed by a rest and a note with a sharp sign.

Handwritten musical notation for the first system, consisting of four staves. The top staff has a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp (F#). It contains two measures of music with chords and a fermata. The second staff has a bass clef and contains two measures of music with chords and a fermata. The third staff has a treble clef and contains two measures of music with chords and a fermata. The fourth staff has a bass clef and contains two measures of music with chords and a fermata.

Handwritten musical notation for the second system, consisting of four staves. The top staff has a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp (F#). It contains two measures of music with chords and a fermata. The second staff has a bass clef and contains two measures of music with chords and a fermata. The third staff has a treble clef and contains two measures of music with chords and a fermata. The fourth staff has a bass clef and contains two measures of music with chords and a fermata.

Handwritten musical notation for the third system, consisting of four staves. The top staff has a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp (F#). It contains two measures of music with chords and a fermata. The second staff has a bass clef and contains two measures of music with chords and a fermata. The third staff has a treble clef and contains two measures of music with chords and a fermata. The fourth staff has a bass clef and contains two measures of music with chords and a fermata.

Handwritten musical notation on three staves. The top staff is mostly empty with some horizontal lines. The middle and bottom staves contain rhythmic patterns of eighth and sixteenth notes, often grouped with slurs. There are several sharp symbols (#) scattered throughout the notation.

Handwritten musical notation on three staves. The top staff is mostly empty. The middle and bottom staves contain rhythmic patterns of eighth and sixteenth notes, often grouped with slurs. There are several sharp symbols (#) scattered throughout the notation.

Handwritten musical notation on three staves. The top staff is mostly empty. The middle staff contains a few notes and rests, with some sharp symbols (#) and a handwritten '3' above a note. The bottom staff contains rhythmic patterns of eighth and sixteenth notes, often grouped with slurs. There are several sharp symbols (#) scattered throughout the notation.

Handwritten musical score for the first system, consisting of four staves. The notation is complex, featuring many accidentals (sharps and naturals) and rhythmic markings. The first staff has a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp (F#). The second staff has a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp. The third and fourth staves have a bass clef and a key signature of one sharp. The notation includes various note values, rests, and dynamic markings.

Handwritten musical score for the second system, consisting of four staves. The notation is complex, featuring many accidentals and rhythmic markings. The first staff has a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp. The second staff has a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp. The third and fourth staves have a bass clef and a key signature of one sharp. The word "trump" is written above the second staff. The notation includes various note values, rests, and dynamic markings.

Handwritten musical score for the third system, consisting of four staves. The notation is complex, featuring many accidentals and rhythmic markings. The first staff has a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp. The second staff has a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp. The third and fourth staves have a bass clef and a key signature of one sharp. The notation includes various note values, rests, and dynamic markings.

Handwritten musical score system 1, consisting of four staves. The top staff contains a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes, including accidentals like sharps and naturals. The second staff features a dense texture of sixteenth notes. The third staff has a melodic line with some rests. The bottom staff contains a bass line with notes and rests. The system concludes with a double bar line and a fermata over the final note.

Handwritten musical score system 2, consisting of four staves. The top staff continues the melodic line with various rhythmic values and accidentals. The second staff shows a more active bass line with eighth notes. The third staff features a long, sweeping melodic line with many sixteenth notes. The bottom staff has a bass line with some rests and a fermata at the end of the system.

Handwritten musical score system 3, consisting of four staves. The top staff continues the melodic line with many sixteenth notes. The second staff has a bass line with some rests and a fermata. The third staff features a melodic line with eighth notes and some accidentals. The bottom staff has a bass line with some rests and a fermata at the end of the system.

Handwritten musical score for the first system, consisting of four staves. The top staff has a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp (F#). The second staff has a bass clef and a key signature of one sharp. The third and fourth staves have a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp. The music includes various note values, rests, and slurs.

Handwritten musical score for the second system, consisting of four staves. The top staff has a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp (F#). The second staff has a bass clef and a key signature of one sharp. The third and fourth staves have a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp. The music includes various note values, rests, and slurs.

Handwritten musical score for the third system, consisting of four staves. The top staff has a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp (F#). The second staff has a bass clef and a key signature of one sharp. The third and fourth staves have a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp. The music includes various note values, rests, and slurs.

Handwritten musical notation for the first system, featuring four staves with treble clefs and a key signature of one sharp (F#). The notation includes various rhythmic patterns, including triplets and sixteenth-note runs.

Handwritten musical notation for the second system, featuring four staves with treble clefs and a key signature of one sharp (F#). The notation includes complex rhythmic patterns, including sixteenth-note runs and triplets.

Handwritten musical notation for the third system, featuring four staves with treble clefs and a key signature of one sharp (F#). The notation includes complex rhythmic patterns, including sixteenth-note runs and triplets.

Handwritten musical score for the first system. The top staff contains a complex melodic line with many sixteenth notes, some beamed together, and some notes with sharp signs. The lower three staves are mostly empty, with some rests and a few notes.

Adagissimo (♩=84)

Handwritten musical score for the second system, marked *Adagissimo* (♩=84). The top staff features a melodic line with a *rit.....* marking. The lower staves have rests and some notes. A key signature change to one sharp (F#) is indicated by a sharp sign on the top staff.

Presto (♩=72)

Handwritten musical score for the third system, marked *Presto* (♩=72). The top staff features a melodic line with a 3/4 time signature. The lower staves have rests and some notes. A key signature change to one sharp (F#) is indicated by a sharp sign on the top staff.

Handwritten musical score for the first system. The top staff contains a complex melodic line with many sixteenth notes and slurs. The lower three staves are mostly empty, with some rests and a few notes.

Adagio

Handwritten musical score for the second system. The top staff continues the melodic line with 'rit.....' markings. The lower three staves show rhythmic patterns, including triplets and quarter notes, with 'rit.....' markings below them.

Maestoso (♩=92)

Handwritten musical score for the third system. The top staff features a complex melodic line with many sixteenth notes and slurs. The lower three staves show rhythmic accompaniment with quarter notes and eighth notes.

Molto Adagio (♩ = 88)

Handwritten musical score for the first system, consisting of four staves. The top staff contains a melodic line with slurs and ties. The three lower staves contain a rhythmic accompaniment with various note values and rests.

Handwritten musical score for the second system, consisting of four staves. The top staff has a few notes followed by a thick vertical bar. The lower staves have notes and rests, also ending with a thick vertical bar.